

ANALYSIS OF HYDROLOGICAL DROUGHT IN THE TURKISH LAKES REGION WITH SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, with the development of remote sensing technologies, it has become easy to detect and analyse changes in the earth. Satellites orbiting around the Earth in certain orbits provide users images with high temporal, spatial and spectral resolution, supporting studies to determine the characteristics, locations, changes over time and deformations of objects in the land. Drought is a disaster that develops in a long time but its effects are very large. The changes caused by this disaster on the earth can be recorded by the mentioned satellite systems. In this study, the water level changes of Lake Burdur, Lake Salda, Lake Akgöl and Lake Yarışlı in the Turkish Lakes Region were analysed over the years due to drought. In the analysis, the images provided by the Sentinel-2 satellite, three images from the dry and wet seasons in each year between 2015 and 2022, were used. Water withdrawal in the lakes due to drought was determined with the help of four different radiometric water indices: NDWI, MNDWI, MNDWI+5 and AWEI. As a result of the analyses, it was concluded that there was a significant loss of water mass over time in the lakes examined, and that these losses were a direct result of drought; and it was seen that the Sentinel-2 satellite images and NDWI, MNDWI, MNDWI +5, AWEI indices used were suitable and practical for change analyses.

Keywords: Turkish Lakes Region, Climate Change, Hydrological Drought, Remote Sensing, Sentinel-2.

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INTRODUCTION

The effects of global warming, which is one of the important environmental problems of the world, have become more evident in recent years with the increase in population and temperatures, decrease in precipitation and deterioration of precipitation regimes. It is possible to see these negative effects with the occurrence of drought in wetlands, especially rivers and lakes. Especially in arid and semi-arid regions, some lakes and wetlands either dry up completely or shrink gradually as a result of water withdrawal. Türkiye has hundreds of lakes, large and small, and is one of the countries where lakes and wetlands are under serious threat by experiencing the effects of climate change and environmental pressures. As a matter of fact, it is possible to see this result clearly throughout the Lakes Region where the study was conducted.

Remote sensing systems provide us with great convenience for drought monitoring thanks to the images recorded from satellites. The behaviour of the formations on the ground surface (water, soil, plants, etc.) according to the signals coming from satellites is different. In order to infer information about an object, that object should not absorb the signals from the satellite, but reflect them and send them back to the satellite. Accordingly, the degree of reflectivity of each object at different wavelengths also varies. This is the basic principle of the detection of objects on the land. The behaviour of objects to which electromagnetic radiation is sent at different wavelengths according to these wavelengths shows us what that object is. Therefore, satellites with multi-spectral characteristics are an important criterion for the detection of objects, and therefore for the detection of changes in different time intervals. Satellites with high spectral resolution have a higher number of objects that can be selected on the ground. In addition, spatial resolution is also an important factor in collecting adequate data. Spatial resolution is related to the size of a pixel. When the size of the pixel is reduced, the number of pixels per detail increases. Thus, that detail can be detected more accurately. In this study, archive data were collected from Sentinel-2 satellite, which is suitable for all these features, between 2015 and 2022. NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index), MNDWI (Modified Normalized Difference Water Index), MNDWI+5 (Modified Normalized Difference Water Index V) and AWEI (Automated Water Extraction Index) water radiometric indices were used in the analysis process. These indices help to determine the boundaries of water covered areas and to create water masks. For this purpose, water radiometric indices were calculated separately over the images collected for dry and wet seasons in the specified time interval and water masks were created to visualise and analyse the loss of water areas over the years. Thanks to the calculated water radiometric indices, it was possible to graphically express the change by creating time series.

In the literature, there are many studies on the use of remote sensing technologies to investigate water anomalies. Salimi (2022) monitored drought in the Lake Urmia basin in Iran over 20 years of data obtained from the MODIS satellite covering the years 2000-2020, and analysed the effects of drought on water bodies and agricultural areas. In the analysis, NDWI index was used for the extraction of

water bodies and it was determined that Lake Urmia had a maximum area in 2000 and a minimum area in 2014. As a result, it was suggested that NDWI and NDVI indices are suitable indices for changes in vegetation and water areas. As another example, Nsubuga (2017) used images from Landsat archive data for the years 1986, 1995 and 2010 to determine the change of water areas on Lake Kyoga Basin in Uganda. He used the MNDWI index by processing the TM and ETM+ spectral bands of the Landsat satellite image. As a result of the analyses, it was revealed that the change in surface water areas is related to the variation in the amount of precipitation. Lu (2013) used 40 years of archive Landsat MSS/TM/ETM+ and HJ-1A/B images collected between 1973 and 2011 to calculate the change in water levels on Lake Baiyangdian in North China. In the study, MNDWI and NDWI indices were calculated, and results showed that the water volumes estimated from the analysis using remote sensing technology were consistent with the volumes obtained from the appropriate equation of the lake storage capacity curve based on observed data. In another study, Meshram (2022) used a combination of Sentinel-2 (2015-2020) and Landsat-8 (2013-2020) satellite imagery to monitor the water surface and assess the severity of drought risk for the Idriss 1 Dam in northeast Morocco. Schwathe (2019) continued the example and introduced a new approach in his study. In the study on Lake Ray Roberts, images from Landsat and Sentinel-2 satellites for the years 1984-2018 were first collected. Land-water masks were extracted by combining five water indices and calculating an automatic threshold. Then, all data gaps due to clouds, cloud shadows or snow-covered surfaces in the image were filled with a water probability mask to obtain a gap-free surface area time series for the lake. The results obtained with this new approach were validated by comparing the surface area changes with the water level time series obtained from the gauging stations. This resulted in a quality improvement for the estimated land-water masks and a reliable data gap filling approach. As an example of studies in Türkiye, Özelkan (2019) analysed the change of water areas in Atikhisar Dam Lake using Landsat-8 OLI satellite images between 2013-2017. NDWI index was used in the analysis. Kaya and Kaplan (2021) obtained images from Landsat-7, Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 satellites between 2009-2019, calculated and analysed the NDWI index to determine the areal change in Lake Burdur. The results showed that Lake Burdur lost 17 km² of area between 2009-2019. In addition, seasonal images were obtained between 2017-2019, and a decrease of 2 km² in water area was observed between spring and autumn seasons. Bahadır (2013) used Landsat images in 5-year periods between 1975 and 2010 to evaluate the spatial changes in Lake Akşehir and used the controlled classification technique in the analyses. While the area of the lake was determined as 314 km² in 1975, it was observed that the area was 119 km² in 2010. As a result of the study, climate parameters were also evaluated and it was determined that this decrease was closely related to the decrease in precipitation, increase in evaporation, increase in water use in the basin and decrease in river flow rates.

In this study, a drought analysis was carried out on Lake Burdur, Lake Salda, Lake Yarıklı and Akgöl in the Turkish Lakes Region by using NDWI, MNDWI, MNDWI+5 and AWEI indices obtained from Sentinel-2 satellite covering the period between 2015-2022.

1. METHODOLOGY

Satellite remote sensing data are widely used as an effective instrument for the detection of water bodies. The images that can be obtained constantly from satellites can be analysed by various pre-processing processes and the change of water bodies between a certain period can be monitored. The lakes analysed in this study are affected by the bad consequences of drought with significant water withdrawal. In order to accurately analyse the water withdrawal in a lake, it is necessary to collect images from both dry and wet seasons during the year. Because in the normal cycle of the ecosystem, while there is a decrease in water areas due to increasing temperatures during the dry season, lakes can fill up again during the rainy season. However, it is possible that this cycle may gradually lose its normalcy due to drought. Therefore, it is necessary to make a comprehensive analysis of the region from the data collected by remote sensing techniques and to determine whether the changes in long periods are significant. For this purpose, water radiometric indices were used to identify water bodies and to create masks of water areas. Water radiometric indices are calculated with various band combinations and are an effective method used in the detection of water covered areas and therefore drought analyses. Thus, it is necessary to collect data from a satellite with a wide spectral range. In general, water reflects only in the visible light range, as can be seen in Figure 1. Since water has almost no reflection in the near infrared range, it is very different from other surfaces. Due to this absorption property, water bodies and features containing water can be easily detected by remote sensing.

Figure 1. Reflection intervals of water and some other objects (URL-1).

In order to identify water bodies, NDWI, MNDWI, MNDWI+5 and AWEI radiometric water indices were calculated for all 23 images collected in the study, generated from Sentinel-2 data. These indices were then used to create a water mask based on the results of the response of water to certain band combinations. The radiometric water indices calculated in this study can be briefly described as follows:

NDWI is used to identify surface waters and measure their extent (Gao, 1996). In this index, water bodies have maximum reflectance in the green band and minimum reflectance in the near infrared

band. NDWI effectively improves water information in most cases. At the same time, it is sensitive to land development and can lead to over-estimation of water bodies (Ksherti, 2018). The NDWI index is calculated as in Eq.1.

$$NDWI = \frac{(Green - NIR)}{(Green + NIR)} \quad (1)$$

MNDWI has emerged as a new approach due to the possibility that the water bodies extracted with NDWI index may be inaccurate as a result of being affected by noise in built-up areas (Xu, 2006). Here, based on the fact that the absorbability of water bodies is higher in the SWIR band than in the NIR band, and that built-up areas have higher reflectance in the SWIR band than in the NIR band, MNDWI was developed. The MNDWI index is calculated as in Eq.2.

$$MNDWI = \frac{(Green - SWIR)}{(Green + SWIR)} \quad (2)$$

MNDWI+5 has emerged as a modification of the Modified Normalised Vegetation Index. It uses red and NIR bands. As a combination of the Enhanced Vegetation Index and the Normalised Vegetation Index, it has the ability to detect the distributions of surface water features more precisely. In this way, it has a great impact in areas such as flood mapping and monitoring of water resources. Unlike the other radiometric water indices mentioned above, surface waters have negative values (<0) in this index. The MNDWI + 5 index is calculated as in Eq.3.

$$MNDWI + 5 = \frac{(NIR - Red)}{(NIR + Red)} \quad (3)$$

The main objective of the AWEI index is to maximise the separability of water and non-water pixels using band difference, addition and application of different coefficients. Accordingly, two separate equations have been suggested to effectively suppress non-water pixels and extract surface water with better accuracy (Feyisa et al., 2013). The AWEI index is calculated as in Eqs.4-5.

$$AWEI_{nsh} = 4(Green - SWIR1) - (0.25NIR + 2.75SWIR2) \quad (4)$$

$$AWEI_{sh} = Blue + 2.5Green - 1.5(NIR + SWIR1) - 0.25SWIR2 \quad (5)$$

2. DATA AND ANALYSIS

The study area, the Turkish Lakes Region, is located in the Mediterranean region between 37°01'-38°30" North latitude and 29°33'-32°21' East longitude. The area of this region, which contains dozens of lakes, is approximately 1.711.250 ha. Lakes constitute 10% of the region with an area of 172.160 ha. The most important reason for the selection of the Turkish Lakes Region as the study area is that 20 of the 36 lakes in this region, located within the borders of Afyonkarahisar-Antalya-Burdur-Denizli-Isparta-Konya, have completely dried up in the last 30 years. The surface areas and water

levels of 16 lakes have decreased significantly due to natural effects such as changes in precipitation regimes due to climate change in the region, decreases in the amount of precipitation, and increased evaporation due to temperature increases, lakes are also in danger of extinction due to anthropogenic activities. Both the surface area and water quality of the remaining 16 lakes are decreasing day by day due to effects such as water diversions for agriculture, lake drying for agriculture, improper land use, eutrophication, dam construction, agricultural irrigation, increased salinity as a result of unconscious use of groundwater, deterioration of the lake ecosystem due to damage to biological habitat and inability to renew itself (Kesici, 2020). The satellite image of the study area is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Study area Turkish Lakes Region.

Sentinel-2A Level 1C images were downloaded from the Sentinel Scientific Data Hub (Sci-Hub) and consist of 13 spectral bands with 10m, 20m and 60m spatial resolution. As shown in Table 1, this spectrum includes wavelengths between 443-2190 nm.

In order to obtain objective results on the change of water levels, images of the 4 lakes mentioned in Figure 2 in the Turkish Lakes Region; between 2015-2022, 3 images for each year were downloaded on dates when wet and dry periods can be easily selected. These images were processed with SNAP and QGIS software. Information about the downloaded images is presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Sentinel-2 satellite spectral bands.

Sentinel-2 Bands	Wavelengths (μm)	Spatial Resolution (m)
B1- Ultra blue (coastal and aerosol)	0.443	60
B2- Blue	0.490	10
B3- Green	0.560	10
B4- Red	0.665	10
B5- Vegetation red edge	0.705	20
B6- Vegetation red edge	0.740	20
B7- Vegetation red edge	0.783	20
B8- NIR	0.842	10
B8A- Narrow NIR	0.865	20
B9- Water vapour	0.945	60
BANT 10- SWIR Cirrus	1.375	60
BANT 11- SWIR	1.610	20
BANT 12- SWIR	2.190	20

The workflow diagram showing the analysis steps in SNAP software for the downloaded images is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. SNAP software workflow diagram.

In the diagram in Figure 3, the atmospheric correction process that follows the data obtaining step is of great importance. Solar radiation reflected from the Earth's surface to satellite sensors is affected by its interaction with the atmosphere. The purpose of an atmospheric correction is to remove atmospheric effects and determine the true surface (sub-atmospheric) reflectance values from above-atmosphere reflectance values. Atmospheric correction is particularly important where multi-temporal imagery is being compared and analysed, as in this study. In order to utilise the unique potential of Sentinel-2 data for field applications and to ensure the highest quality scientific use, satellite imagery needs to be correctly corrected for atmospheric effects (Main-Knorn, 2017).

Table 2. Data used in the study.

Date	Season	Image File Name
29.08.2015	Dry	S2A_MSIL1C_20150829T085006_N0204_R107_T35SQB_20150829T085004
27.12.2015	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20151227T085402_N0201_R107_T35SQB_20151227T085356
05.04.2016	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20160405T085012_N0201_R107_T35SQB_20160405T085750
03.08.2016	Dry	S2A_MSIL1C_20160803T084602_N0204_R107_T35SQB_20160803T085152
11.12.2016	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20161211T085342_N0204_R107_T35SQB_20161211T085344
10.04.2017	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20170410T084601_N0204_R107_T35SQB_20170410T085422
08.08.2017	Dry	S2A_MSIL1C_20170808T084601_N0205_R107_T35SQB_20170808T085345
26.12.2017	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20171226T085351_N0206_R107_T35SQB_20171226T105255
05.04.2018	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20180405T084601_N0206_R107_T35SQB_20180407T161935
13.08.2018	Dry	S2A_MSIL1C_20180813T084601_N0206_R107_T35SQB_20180813T115419
31.12.2018	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20181231T085351_N0207_R107_T35SQB_20181231T091844
30.04.2019	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20190430T084601_N0207_R107_T35SQB_20190430T105234
08.08.2019	Dry	S2A_MSIL1C_20190808T084601_N0208_R107_T35SQB_20190808T110902
06.12.2019	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20191206T085341_N0208_R107_T35SQB_20191206T091914
14.04.2020	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20200414T084601_N0209_R107_T35SQB_20200414T102346
02.08.2020	Dry	S2A_MSIL1C_20200802T084601_N0209_R107_T35SQB_20200802T110352
10.11.2020	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20201110T085211_N0209_R107_T35SQB_20201110T101315
19.05.2021	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20210519T084601_N0300_R107_T35SQB_20210519T124459
27.08.2021	Dry	S2A_MSIL1C_20210827T084601_N0301_R107_T35SQB_20210827T093634
15.11.2021	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20211115T085231_N0301_R107_T35SQB_20211115T100049
14.04.2022	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20220414T084601_N0400_R107_T35SQB_20220414T105758
12.08.2022	Dry	S2A_MSIL1C_20220812T084611_N0400_R107_T35SQB_20220812T123327
30.12.2022	Wet	S2A_MSIL1C_20221230T085351_N0509_R107_T35SQB_20221230T104906

The images obtained from the Sentinel-2 satellite are classified as Level 1C and Level 2A. This classification is based on the presence or absence of atmospheric correction. Level 1C images are upper-atmosphere reflections obtained since the Sentinel satellites were first launched into space. In other words, they are not atmospherically corrected. Level 2A images are atmospherically and radiometrically corrected images (reflections below the atmosphere). While Level 2A images were initially available only in the European region, the scope increased in 2019 and reached a global dimension. However, if the analysis to be performed is older than these years, Level 1C images can be obtained and manually atmospherically corrected. In this study, the images were downloaded as Level 1C and atmospheric corrections were made with the Sen2Cor toolbox in the SNAP software.

Another point to be emphasised in the diagram is the “resampling” process. With this process, the bands of the Sentinel-2 satellite that do not have the same resolution are brought to equal resolution.

In the last step of determination of water areas and creation of water masks; it can be said that NDWI, MNDWI and AWEI indices show water feature in places with values greater than 0, while MNDWI+5 index shows water feature in places with values less than 0.

3. RESULTS

Temperature and precipitation data for the region were obtained from NASA's POWER (Prediction of Worldwide Energy Resource) Data Access Viewer site in order to interpret the results in a meaningful way. As a result, graphs were created over the data. The graph showing the total precipitation between 2015-2022 is presented in Figure 4 and the graph showing the monthly average temperatures between the same years is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Annual Total Precipitation between 2015-2022.

As seen in Figure 4, the total amount of precipitation in 2015 was 622.22 mm. This amount decreased to 416.6 mm in 2017, the lowest value in the time interval we have chosen in the study. While it increases and decreases again in the following years, it is finally displayed as 546.7 mm in 2022. The difference in precipitation between 2015 and 2022 is 75.57 mm.

Figure 5. Changes in Average Monthly Temperature between 2015-2022.

Another parameter, temperature, is also an effect that should be interpreted in drought analyses. When we look at the graph showing the average monthly temperatures between 2015 and 2022 in Figure 5, it can be said that there has been an increase in temperatures in recent years. In 8 out of 12 months, the temperatures in 2015 are lower than the temperatures in 2022. It is also seen that there are increases in the time between these two years.

The area of Lake Burdur, the first of the analysed lakes, showed a continuous decrease between 2015 and 2022. Previously, it was noticed that the decrease in water levels in the dry summer months could be considered normal, and this loss was compensated when the rain and snow season started. However, as 2022 came closer, the decline in water levels continued in the winter and autumn periods when precipitation should be high. Therefore, it can be said that the decreasing amount of precipitation due to global warming and drought is not sufficient for the lakes to reach their full water capacity.

The temporal area change graph of Lake Burdur is presented in Figure 6. According to this, the date when the lake had the maximum area was 27 December 2015, while the date when it had the minimum area was 30 December 2022. The area of the water mass lost over the years for Lake Burdur is 16.679 km².

Figure 6. Time-based change in water area of Lake Burdur.

The comparison of the image dated 27.12.2015 with the maximum water area of Lake Burdur and the image dated 30.12.2022 with the minimum water area is as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Lake Burdur maximum and minimum area comparison.

The second lake analysed is Lake Yarışlı. Lake Yarışlı is one of the lakes in the region that is rapidly losing water masses. In the time-dependent area change graph in Figure 8, it was determined that the lake was close to complete drying between 2020-2021, and after an increase in the area in April 2022, it reached the drying stage again in the summer. The dates of maximum and minimum areas are 5 April 2016 and 19 May 2021, respectively. The difference in area lost between these dates is 14.779 km².

Figure 8. Time-based change in the water area of Lake Yarışlı.

The image dated 30 December 2022 and the image dated 5 April 2014 were used for the maximum and minimum area comparison of Lake Yarışlı, respectively, and are presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Comparison of maximum and minimum area in Lake Yarışlı.

The third lake analysed is Akgöl. Akgöl is one of the completely dried lakes in the region. As seen in Figure 10, the lake, which had a maximum area on 5 April 2016, completely dried up after 14 April 2020 and its area was determined as 0 km² as of 2 August 2020. The maximum and minimum area difference is 8.581 km².

Figure 10. Time-based change in water area of Akgöl.

Figure 11 shows a visual of the lake when it had maximum area and its final state before it dried up.

Figure 11. Akgöl maximum and minimum area comparison.

The last lake analysed in the study is Lake Salda. Lake Salda has also started to gradually decrease in area. Although it is seen in Figure 12 that the lake continues to protect its area in a general line, it is obvious that there are fluctuations in between. The maximum area is seen on 29 August 2015 and the minimum area is seen on 12 August 2022. The sudden decrease in December 2016 is also not overlooked. The maximum and minimum area difference is 5,572 km².

Figure 12. Time-based change in water area of Lake Salda.

Figure 13 shows the image dated 29.08.2015, when Salda Lake had the maximum area, and the image dated 12.08.2022 to see its state in a period close to the present day. The area difference between these two dates is 1.868 km².

Figure 13. Lake Salda maximum and minimum area comparison.

CONCLUSIONS

Due to drought, which is a common problem of our era, our lakes, which are used for drinking-household water, irrigation water in agriculture, industrial use water, commercial and sportive fishing area, recreation, tourism, water sports area, hydroelectric energy production, salt and various mineral substance production source, and which are used for vital, socio-economic development and industrialisation purposes, are disappearing. The lakes in the region known as the Turkish Lakes Region, which contains many lakes, have also been greatly affected by this situation. Dozens of lakes in this region have dried up and most of them are in danger of drying up. Within the scope of this study, drought analysis of four lakes selected from the Turkish Lakes Region was carried out and temporal changes in water level were analysed.

Based on the analysed output data; it can be said that there has been a continuous decrease in the lakes, which previously had a fluctuation in water levels but can increase again. In the study, analyses were made over a period of 6 years. However, since the climate effect does not occur in a short period of time, longer-term data should be analysed to establish a definite connection with drought. On these short-term changes in water levels, it can be said that the use of water from lakes for irrigation for agricultural purposes, the establishment of polluting facilities around the lakes, in short, human-induced effects are more intense. In the analysed Lake Burdur, Lake Yarışlı, Akgöl and Lake Salda, the maximum and minimum area differences in the time interval determined for the study (2015-2022) are 16.679 km², 14.779 km², 8.581 km² and 5.572 km², respectively. These losses are extremely serious for lakes, which are an important element of our ecosystem.

In this context, Kaya and Kaplan (2021) conducted a study on the areal change in Lake Burdur and found that the lake lost approximately 10 km² of area between 2015-2019. In addition, Sağır (2023) obtained supportive results in his study on Lake Burdur. These results are consistent with the results of this study. Since the method used for Lake Burdur is the same for all lakes, it can be said that the results in the analysis of other lakes in our study are also consistent. Aksoy, Sarı and Çabuk (2019) analysed four lakes in the Turkish Lakes Region to determine the change in water levels in lakes. In their study, they used Landsat-8 images between 2013 and 2013 to determine the wetlands with the NDWI index. As a result, they detected a 2.8 km withdrawal in the northwestern parts of Lake Burdur. They stated that agricultural activities are intensive in this region and water withdrawals may be due to the active use of the lake water for this purpose. An analysis was also made for Lake Yarışlı in this study. It was determined that Lake Yarışlı also lost a large amount of water from all aspects and that agricultural activities were high in the western parts where this loss was experienced. All these results are in the same way with our study. Lastly, Sabuncu (2020), in his study on Lake Burdur with remote sensing, used Landsat images from 1986, 1997, 2008 and 2019 to determine the water areas with the MNDWI index. In order to make a comparison with our study, if the results of 2019 in both studies are considered; Sabuncu (2020) determined that Lake Burdur had an area of 125 km² in 2019, while

this result is 125.115 km² for December 2019 in our study. When the results are compared, it is seen that this study also gives similar results with our study.

Remote sensing systems have provided great convenience in visualising the earth with the developing technology. As a result of this study, it was observed that the Sentinel-2 satellite, which can pass through the same point every 5 days, is fast and suitable for analysing and monitoring the temporal changes of the results of a slow natural disaster such as drought.

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